

Reactivity of phenylmercury-*O,O'*-alkylenedithiophosphate

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The interactions of phenylmercury-*O,O'*-alkylenedithiophosphate [$C_6H_5HgS(S)POCH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2O$] with various *O*- and *S*-donor Lewis bases have yielded some new molecular adducts.

Our continuing interest in the reactivity of organometal *O,O'*-alkylenedithiophosphates¹⁻³ led us to examine the reactivity of [$C_6H_5HgS(S)POCH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2O$] towards several *O*- and *S*-donor ligands, such as dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethylformamide (DMF), 2,6-lutidine-*N*-oxide (2,6-Lu-O), 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (1-Me-2-pyr), triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO), dimethylacetamide (DMA), antipyrine (ap), thiourea (Tu), triphenylphosphine sulfide (TPPS) and tetramethylthiuramdisulfide (Me_4tds).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data correspond to 1 : 1 (metal dtp : base) stoichiometry. The adducts are crystalline solid, thermally and hydrolytically stable, and soluble in common organic solvents. Their non-conducting nature in DMSO ($2.40-6.16 \Omega^{-1} cm^{-1} mol^{-1}$) indicates absence of ionic species in solution.

IR spectra :

IR bands at 1120 [(P)-O-C] and 1050 cm^{-1} [(P-O)(C)] in the parent phenylmercuryalkylene dtp² have consistently been observed at the same region in the molecular adduct. The band due to $\nu_{P=S}$ present in phenylmercuryalkylenedithiophosphate shows almost no shift in the molecular adducts ($580 \pm 4 cm^{-1}$). The ν_{P-S} band shows a small positive shift in the molecular adducts³ ($526 \pm 2 cm^{-1}$). The Hg-S stretching mode of vibration is beyond the recorded range of the spectra.

O-Donors (DMF, DMA, ap, 1-Me, 2-pyr, DMSO, 2,6-Lut-O, TPPO) : The $\nu_{C=O}$ modes in various amide bases⁴ ($1649 \pm 17 cm^{-1}$) undergo negative shift in the spectra of the molecular adducts ($1613 \pm 13 cm^{-1}$), suggesting coordination through the oxygen atom of the bases. A strong intensity band at 1245 cm^{-1} (N=O) in 2,6-lutidine-*N*-oxide suffers a negative shift in the spectrum of the adduct ($1220 cm^{-1}$), suggesting Hg ← O coordination⁵. The presence of coordinated TPPO is established by a negative shift of $\nu_{P=O}$ ⁶. The decrease in the absorption due to $\nu_{S=O}$ in the adducts with DMSO is attributed to the decrease in π -bonding char-

acter of S=O bond, indicating coordination from the oxygen atom of the base⁷.

S-Donors (Me_4tds , Tu and TPPS) : The $\nu_{C=S}$ mode in Me_4tds and Tu appearing at 988 and 1090 cm^{-1} , respectively, undergoes blue-shift on complexation and appears at 980 and 1070 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the adducts, indicating coordination through sulfur atom of the linear thiuram sulfide chain⁸ in case of Me_4tds and Hg ← S bonding⁹ in case of Tu. That TPPS coordinates through its S-atoms is evident from the negative shift of $\nu_{P=S}$ from 639 cm^{-1} in the free base to 630 cm^{-1} in the molecular adducts¹⁰.

PMR spectra :

In the ¹H NMR spectrum of [$C_6H_5HgS(S)POCH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2O$].DMSO, the characteristic proton signals due to aryl group of the Lewis acid remain almost unaffected and appear at δ 7.36–7.15 (m), whereas these due to O-CH₂ and CH₂ shift to high field at δ 4.03–4.02 and 3.39–3.25, respectively, indicating considerable drift of electrons from the Lewis base to the metal atom. The signal at δ 2.33 (s, CH₃) indicates the presence of free rotation about the C-S bond which makes them magnetically equivalent¹¹. The positions and integration of the peaks agree well with the proposed (1 : 1) stoichiometry of the molecular adducts.

The above analytical and spectral studies tentatively indicate the following structure for [$C_6H_5HgS(S)POGO$].L.

The mercury atom in the molecular adducts [$C_6H_5HgS(S)POGO$].L (G = $CH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2-$; L = unidentate base) is three-coordinated^{3,12}.

Experimental

[$C_6H_5HgS(S)POCH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2O$] was synthesised as described earlier². The Lewis bases were obtained from

B.D.H., Eastman and Aldrich. Liquid bases were distilled and solid bases crystallised from suitable solvents. The molar conductance (in DMSO) was measured using a dip-type conductivity cell on a DC 610 conductivity meter. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 and FTIR 1800 spectrophotometers and ^1H NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Bruker WM-400 FT spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

Reaction of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{CH}_2\text{O}]$ with Lewis bases : The molecular adducts were prepared by direct interaction of the Lewis bases with phenylmercury- O,O' -alkylenedithiophosphate in suitable solvent. In a representative experiment, a solution of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{CH}_2\text{O}]$ (4.74 g, 0.01 mol), $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{PO}$ (2.94 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone (10 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for ~5 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the solid obtained by adding petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) was washed with petroleum ether and dried over P_4O_{10} under reduced pressure. Decomp. temp. (°C) of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{CH}_2\text{O}]\cdot\text{L}$ compounds are as follows : where L = DMSO, 124°; L = DMF, 124°; L = 2,6-Lut, 122°; L = 1-Me, 2-Pyr, 125°; L = TPPO, 140°; L = DMA, 123°; L = ap, 145°; L = Tu, 121°; L = Me_4tds , 122°.

All compounds gave satisfactory Hg and S analyses.

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References

1. C. P. Basin, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **77**, L 131; 1987, **128**, 69; T. N. Srivastava, J. D. Singh and S. K. Srivastava, *Phosphorus Sulfur*, 1991, **55**, 117; *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 943.
2. S. K. Srivastava, S. Jain and S. B. Saxena, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1998, **28**, 1431.
3. S. K. Srivastava, S. Jain and S. B. Saxena, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1999, in press.
4. S. K. Srivastava, P. C. Srivastava and N. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 443.
5. D. W. A. Sharp, D. H. Brown and S. J. Amasa, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 2892.
6. S. Miliser and D. Hadzi, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1971, **7**, 745.
7. H. G. Langer and A. H. Blut, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 288.
8. G. Contreas and H. Cartes, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1970, **6**, 225.
9. S. J. Palil, D. B. Sowerby and D. G. Tuck, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1187.
10. T. N. Srivastava and M. N. Pande, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 344.
11. C. E. Holloway and M. H. Gittitz, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 2659.
12. T. N. Srivastava and M. N. Pande, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 810.